

**KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE OF FAMILY PLANNING AMONG
WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE (15-49 YEARS) IN NYAGHASANG COMMUNITY,
CALABAR MUNICIPAL LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, CROSS RIVER STATE,
NIGERIA**

ABSTRACT

Background

The scope of family planning extends beyond the subject of population control to involve the overall health of a nation, especially in Nigeria with one of the highest fertility rate in sub-Saharan Africa. The study was conducted to assess the level of knowledge and attitude and practice of family planning, prevalence of family planning utilization, preferred method of family planning and the determinants of family planning utilization among women of reproductive age in Nyaghasang community.

Material and methods

A cross sectional descriptive survey of 180 women of reproductive age was conducted. Multistage sampling technique was employed to select the study population. In the first stage, 3 major roads were selected using the ballot method. In the second stage, 3 streets were randomly selected from each selected road. In the 3rd stage, all the houses in the selected streets were numbered to create a sampling frame. Sample houses were selected using a systematic sampling method. Occupants of selected houses that met the inclusion criteria were chosen for the study. Pretested, interviewer administered Semi structured questionnaires were used to retrieve data from study population. Data analysis with SPSS 21.0 was done using descriptive statistics to summarize variables while inferential statistics (chi-square) was used to test the association between two categorical variables and level was set at 5%.

Results

The mean age of the respondents was 29.78 ± 8.82 years. Majority of study participants were aware of family planning (88%) with the primary source of information on family planning being friends and relatives (60%). Condoms were the most popular method of family planning (51%). Majority of participants (81.1%) said family planning was good for the reason that it helps in child spacing (36%). Most of the participants were aware of side effects of family planning methods. Family planning prevalence was 41% and the preferred method of family planning was condom (56.7). Fear of side effect (42.2%), partner's consent (22.2%) and religious belief (13.9%) were cited as the main reasons for non-usage of family planning. Educational level of respondents correlates well with the level of knowledge of family planning. However, awareness of family planning, attitude towards family planning and awareness of side effects of family planning methods revealed no statistically significant association with use of family planning.

Conclusion and recommendation

Family planning utilization remains poor despite high level of awareness. Main reason for non-use of family planning was fear of side effects, partners consent and religious belief. Effective educational and counseling interventions are required to improve women's knowledge and subsequent uptake of contraceptive usage. Keywords: Prevalence; determinants; uptake; modern family planning; rural community.

Keywords; family planning, prevalence, contraception.

INTRODUCTION

With a population of about 200.96 million (World Population Review 2019), Nigeria is currently ranked the most populous African nation and the seventh most populous country in the world. This rapidly increasing population growth rate is not without its ills and cons, one of which

is the constant struggle for survival amidst economic hardship as there is a significant lag in socioeconomic growth rate.

The Who defined family planning as "the ability of individuals and couples to anticipate and attain their desired number of children and spacing and timing of their birth, achieved through the use of contraceptive methods and the treatment of involuntary infertility." (World Health Organisation Department of Reproductive Health and Research 2011). It can also be defined as educational, comprehensive medical or social activities which enable individuals and couples to determine freely the number and spacing of their children and to select the means by which this may be achieved. (Ayele et Al 2018) described it as a conscious effort by a couple to limit or space the number of children they have through the use of contraceptive methods.

Family planning services are available at all levels of health care in Nigeria, and these services ranges from reversible methods (such as natural, hormonal and barrier methods et cetera) which are well embraced and commonly used, to irreversible methods (such as vasectomy and tubal ligation) which are viewed with high degree of skepticism by majority of the population, even amongst health care practitioners. The various methods and practices through which family planning can be achieved, provides a variety of options to choose from with factors such as age, marital and educational status, availability, potency, side effect and reversibility of method, as well as socioeconomic factors including cultural and religious concerns, affecting to a large extent the selection of the method of choice.

It is important to note that in as much as family planning centers primarily around female reproductive health, knowledge and practice of family planning is not restricted to the women alone as it also includes some methods and practices that incorporates the male sex. Thus effective awareness and optimal utilization of these methods and practices requires that both women and men be well informed. Also, family planning services are not restricted to married couples as they are not necessarily used to 'plan a family' alone, and as such are also made available to unmarried individuals who do not intend to start or have a family.

Despite an increase in the implementation of family planning worldwide and in the awareness on the usefulness and importance of family planning, contraceptive use is still very low in many developing countries of which Nigeria is not an exemption. Contraceptive utilization rate in

Nigeria falls within a range of 11% - 15%, with an even lower value recorded in northern parts (Monjok, Smensy, Ekabua and Essien 2012; NDHS 2013). Many factors have been associated with the low utilization rate in developing countries, including lack of access, opposition by spouse, fear of side effects, religious and cultural disapproval. These low utilization rates in many developing countries have been identified with high fertility rates which in turn have been identified with high rates of maternal, infant and child mortality.

The importance of family planning can be seen at individual, family and communal levels. Family planning prevents undesired pregnancies, indirectly helping to reduce the incidence of unsafe abortion especially in developing countries where it is a major contributor to maternal mortality.

To the family, raising a child requires resources in different forms, including time, finance, environmental and social. Adequate birth spacing helps to efficiently manage these resources so that there are equal opportunities and adequate care for all. Also, achieving adequate birth spacing could reduce child mortality by 20 percent or more, particularly in developing countries with myriads of socioeconomic problems (World Health Organisation 2001). Family planning has attracted global attention and has been widely adopted throughout the world. It has been identified as a key step in the prevention of unintended pregnancies, maternal mortality, infant mortality and over population.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Unwanted pregnancies account for about 40% of pregnancies worldwide and a greater part of this percentage end in induced abortion which is illegal in Nigeria. But this does not stop its occurrence, with majority of such cases carried out under unsafe conditions. Nigeria has one of the highest maternal mortality ratios in sub-Saharan Africa and ranks as the country with the second highest maternal deaths in the world, with unsafe abortion contributing to 20-40% of about 60,000 maternal deaths that occur yearly in Nigeria (Monjok, Smensy, Ekabua and Essien 2012). Traditional practices accounts for 49% of maternal mortality in Calabar as well as poor health care delivery leads to high maternal mortality rate and accounts for 83.6% of the variation in maternal mortality rate in Calabar (Akpabio et al 2020). In addition to unsafe abortion, high risk pregnancies are another group that contribute to maternal mortality in Nigeria and both can be prevented via adequate utilization of family planning services by preventing the occurrence of

pregnancy altogether. There is also an established link between the high infant mortality rate and the low family planning services utilization rate in many developing countries.

Nigeria is currently ranked as the 20th poorest country in the world with a current GDP per capita of 5,927 US dollars, reflecting a poor socioeconomic growth rate as opposed to a robust population growth rate. Reijhen et al recognised uncontrolled population growth as a single most important impediment to a nation's development. Studies have also shown an association between high poverty levels and high fertility and population growth rates in developing countries where practise of family planning is low. (Imelda, Green, Cucuzza, 2009; Ujira 2012).

Promotion of family planning especially in countries with high fertility rate, has the potential to reduce to a significant level, poverty, maternal and childhood morbidity and mortality rates, thus signifying the need to assess the knowledge and practice of family planning among women of reproductive age.

1.3 Purpose of Study

General objective

To investigate the knowledge, attitude and practice of family planning among women of reproductive age (15-49years) in Nyaghasang community, Calabar, Nigeria.

Specific objectives

1. To determine the level of knowledge of women of reproductive age, towards family planning services in Nyaghasang community.
2. To determine the factors influencing the attitude towards family planning among women of reproductive age in Nyaghasang community.
3. To identify the factors affecting the practice of family planning among women of reproductive

age in Nyaghasang community.

1.4 Significance of Study

The recorded low levels of knowledge of family planning services as revealed from literature prompted this study. Moreover, there is meagreness of information concerning any such study in Nyanghasang community despite the fact that this community has health facilities offering family planning services.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Family planning is a voluntary, and available method of contraception (previously referred to as birth control), customize to individual needs with a range of methods that are acceptable to all and effective if used correctly (Dorothy 2010, World Health Organisation 2015).

Family planning is hailed as one of the great public health achievements of the last century and worldwide acceptance has risen to three-fifths of exposed couples (Tsui *et al.*, 2010). Family planning is an aspect of family health aimed at promoting reproductive health and preventing consequences. The objective of which is to encourage couples to take responsible decisions about pregnancies and enable them achieve healthy life.

Family planning is sometimes used as a synonym for the use of birth control. It often includes a wide range of methods and practices that are aimed at controlling birth and child spacing. It is usually applied to couples who wish to limit the number of children they have and/or to control the timing of pregnancy (also known as child spacing) and encompasses sterilization as well as abortions (Tsui, et al., 2010).

Contraception can be defined as the means of achieving family planning. It is a voluntary interruption of the chain of event that leads to conception.

2.1 History of Family Planning

The history of contraception is as old as man himself as several historical books including the Bible have mentioned *coitus interruptus* as a means of preventing pregnancy. Periodic abstinence was also used in ancient times when it was discovered that sexual intercourse results in pregnancy.

By the 1800's, spermicidal chemicals, condoms, diaphragms, and intrauterine contraceptive devices (IUCDs) made from silk worms gut began to gain relevance and wide acceptance.

The barrier methods have had great progress with the first polyurethane condoms launched in the United Kingdom (UK) in 1997.

In 2005, a new synthetic non-latex condom was launched in the UK. The early 1900's witnessed the introduction of the hormonal progestin only and combined oral contraceptive pills(COCPs) and the combination of hormones with already existing IUCD's with the injectables being introduced in the 1950's. By the 1970's, emergency contraception using Yuzpe regimen was available. Biphasic and triphasic pills were abundant in the 1980's and by 1993 implants such as Norplant was used followed by the introduction of implanon in 1999. In 2003, a contraceptive patch called Ortho Evra containing ethinylestradiol and norelgestromin was available. Noxplanon, a type of radio opaque implanon was introduced in 2010.

While progress was being made on all these temporary methods of contraception, strides were also being made in the field of sterilization as by the 1972, American Health Service (Family Planning) Amendment Act allowed vasectomy to be carried out on the same basis as other family planning methods (Family planning Association, FPA, 2017).

Female sterilization via abdominal surgery was first carried out by Von Blundell in 1834. Culdoscopy, where the vagina is passed through instead of an incision being made is attributed to Dr. Decker while Dr. T Evans was first to clip the fallopian tubes.

Laparoscopic sterilization was first introduced in 1961 and hysteroscopy in 2002.

In most parts of the world and Nigeria in particular, more than 90% of young people know at least one contraceptive method, but usage rates remain low, especially in rural areas. This is probably due in part, to the lack of youth-friendly services, myths about sexuality and reproductive health, lack of knowledge about sexual and reproductive rights as well as human rights and gender inequality. (Osakinle *et al.*, 2013).

Family planning methods

Contraceptive methods have being broadened and improved in most countries today. Contraceptive choices vary among women, culture, age groups as no one single method of contraception is completely adequate.

An ideal contraceptive must be safe, simple, easy to use, 100% effective, promptly reversible, devoid of side effects, cheap, independent of coitus and acceptable to both couple. However, no

contraceptive method meets all these criteria giving rise to the need for information and counseling.

The various classes of contraceptive method include; Hormonal methods, barrier methods natural methods, voluntary surgical methods, and immunological/ male methods.

The hormonal methods include oral pills, vaginal pessaries, injectable, implants and IUCDs. The barrier methods include male and female condoms, diaphragms, cervical caps, vaginal sponges and spermicides. Natural methods are lactational ammenorhoea method (LAM), cervical mucus or Billing's methods, ovulation and calendar methods.

Voluntary surgical contraceptive methods include tubal ligation, electrocoagulation, use of clips (Fischie) and rings (Falope), use of chemicals and vasectomy. The immunological or male methods involve the use of anti-HCG vaccines, leutenizing hormone-Receptor hormone vaccine (LH/RH vaccine) and gossypol (WHO, 2015).

2.2 Benefits of Family Planning (FP)

The benefits of FP are economic, demographic, health, Economic and demographic rationales are often useful at the national level, however, the health rationale is most acceptable for health development planning and policies.

2.2.1 Health Benefits

Health-wise, family planning is widely acknowledged as an important intervention towards achieving millennium development goals 'four' and 'five' (MDGs4&5) as it has proven to reduces maternal and child mortality (World Health Organisation, 2015). Over 70% of maternal deaths occur in developing countries. However, Family Planning could prevent as many as one in every three maternal deaths by allowing women to delay motherhood, space births, avoid unwanted pregnancies and abortion and stop bearing children when they reach their desired family size (Muluwas, 2015).

When used to space birth at least two years apart, contraceptive save children lives. When births are space for less than two years particularly less than eighteen months, it increase the incidence of

prematurity and low birth weight which can contribute to infant mortality (World Health Organisation, 2015).

2.2.2 Economic Benefits of FP

Family Planning helps to prevent teenage pregnancy by delaying first birth until women are at least eighteen years, reduce the economic and emotional burdens of parenthood (World Health Organisation, 2015).

This is largely because families with fewer healthier children can devote more resources into improving their children by providing adequate food, clothing, housing and education opportunities as opposed to families with many children.

2.2.3 Demographic Benefits of Family Planning

Nigeria is the most populous state in sub-Saharan Africa, with the 2006 census report showing that Nigeria has over two hundred million people with a growth rate of 8% per annum (National Population Commission, 2011). Family Planning is beneficial to nations as it checks population growth rate, prevents human immunodeficiency virus acquired immunodeficiency syndrome, HIV/AIDS transmission and enable better and more efficient utilization of national resources (World Health Organisation, 2015).

2.3 Knowledge and Attitude of Family Planning

Globally, knowledge of FP has increased especially in the developed countries as evidenced by the several studies conducted in these regions (Population Reference Bureau (PRB), 2013).

In less developed nations, several studies in different regions and countries have shown that knowledge of family planning is considerably high. Although there is very high level of awareness in the United States of America as over 90% of women use at least one contraceptive method at some point in time, making contraceptives and family planning important aspect of preventive healthcare for women (Mosher and Jones, 2010; Austine and Mathias, 2011).

A study in Pakistan comprising of a total of 176 women showed that more than 80% were aware of family planning methods especially the use of condoms and about 41% of them knew about the side effects of contraceptive methods (Haider *et al.*, 2009).

A research done on the current attitude of women towards contraceptive in Europe showed that women's unaided awareness of COC pills and male condoms was the highest with 98% and 95% respectively, but that of much newer methods like vaginal rings was very low being less than 30%. That of cervical diaphragm ranged from 16 to 30 %, female condom. Less than one-sixth and less than a tenth had heard about it. A great majority of the women (87%), however, received their information from the internet or doctor's brochures (Johnson *et al.*, 2015).

In India, the cognizance of contraceptives and their benefits is improving as evidenced by a rise a 56% knowledge base in 2011 (Musarat *et al.*, 2011) to 87 in 2014 (Pegu *et at.*, 2014) seen from different studies conducted among the women of reproductive age. This is owed in part to increase literacy rate among women in this region and also due to better utilization of health care services.

In Meghalkya, India, a cross sectional study of 200 married women (15-45 years) were informed about contraception, 58.6% (102) was from health workers, 24.1% (42) was from the media and 15.5% (27) was from the social circle. In this study, condoms were also the most well-known form of contraceptives as about two-thirds of the women knew about it, one-third had heard about OCPs and knowledge of the other methods including tubal ligation each made up only a tenth of the women. The results showed slight disparity from results obtained in Pakistan where 68% of it women had knowledge about tubal ligation as seen in a study done by (Sonia 2009.)

Lapses identified by that study was that up to 94% of women had no knowledge of the safe period which might negatively influence their use of the natural methods.

Another India-based study showed strikingly similar results pointing to a higher rate of knowledge of contraceptive use among female compared with their male counterparts. It revealed that 94.4% of females were knowledgeable about one or more methods of contraception compared to 6% of males. Furthermore, the males (72%) were more knowledgeable about traditional methods compared to 46.4% of females. (Saluja *et al.* 2011).

In Ghana, a survey of 332 women of reproductive age (15-49 years) showed that cognizance of the existence of contraceptives was over 99%, general grasp of contraceptive use was 97% and knowledge of more than three methods was about two-thirds of the sample population. In Ghana also, another cross sectional study using semi-structured interview was done on a group of women of reproductive age (15-49years) in Accra region and showed that less than one-tenth knew at least one method of contraceptive with OCPs and condoms topping the list as best heard although they admitted that these methods had failed them previously.

The setback though is that this study was carried out on a limited sample size and as such wouldn't give a true representation of the rest of the population.

A study on emergency contraception carried out in about 45 countries among women of reproductive age (15-49 years) was analyzed in logistic regressions. Results from this study showed that the lowest proportion of women to have heard of contraception was in Chad (less than 2%) and the highest being in Columbia with two-thirds (66%) (Palermo et al, 2014). 98.8% of Tanzanian women were knowledgeable making them the highest globally (Lwellamira *et al.*, 2012). In Nigeria, there is a good level of awareness and knowledge of contraception as would be shown by the result of variety of studies done on different parts of the population, although therein lies a great disparity in the level of awareness as we traverse the geopolitical zones. For example, up to 80% of grand multiparous women in Kano have knowledge of contraception, their source being midwives. 56% of them have media and a third have doctors as their sources, as seen in a descriptive cross sectional study (Ibrahim et al, 2013). Generally, in Nigeria, younger women age (15-19) and women residing in the north east are least likely to know of a contraceptive method (67% and 73% respectively). As would be expected, knowledge of contraceptive method is higher among women residing in cities (95%) than among those living in villages (78%).

Among the states, awareness of contraceptive methods is lowest for women in Niger (56%) and in Kebbi (51%). Similarly, knowledge of contraceptive methods is lowest among women with no education and those in the lowest wealth quartile (72% and 67% respectively) (Nigerian Demographic Health Survey, NDHS, 2013).

A study conducted in Jos, Nigeria revealed that 88.1% of women attending antenatal clinic were knowledgeable about family planning (Utoo, 2010).

In a study carried out by Oguntona *et al.*, 2013, the knowledge and practice of contraception such as; natural, barrier, hormonal and traditional methods were studied among university undergraduates in Lagos state using structured questionnaires. Sources of information on contraception were also studied alongside choice and use of contraceptives among undergraduates. The result showed that the major source of information on contraceptives was peer group followed by electronic media. Parental contribution on this issue was low. 98% of the respondents had good knowledge about contraceptives, their attitude towards contraceptives was also positive but its use was low with only about 54% practicing contraception and this is probably due to discrimination against adolescents and young adults by family planning providers and low parental influence on contraceptives use.

Several studies in the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria indicates that contraceptive knowledge and awareness, especially among female students aged 15 to 24 years, is very high (Monjok *et al.*, 2010).

In Ilorin, the methods mostly known by respondents were the condoms (69%), the oral contraceptive pills, OCP, (38.8%), IUCD (29%) and periodic abstinence (32.9%), with most respondents being able to name at least one method of contraception.

Knowledge of contraceptives is quiet laudable in the southern part of Nigeria. For instance, in Nnewi, a Southeastern state, 95.5% of women are well informed about contraception (Igwegbe *et al.*, 2009). In Benin city, greater than 85% of women are aware of contraception with 92.8% being well informed of the subject but as many as 7.2%, however, have incorrect knowledge. A general assessment of the level of knowledge based on fair or good knowledge was not done.

Another study in Cross River state was carried out to probe family planning behaviors and decision making among 860 couples (men and women of reproductive ages).

Knowledge of different types of contraceptives among the male and female respondents shows that the contraceptives methods they were aware of are in the following order condom (50%), pills (36.3%), rhythm or periodic abstinence (33.4%), injectable (23.4%), withdrawal method (20.6%), IUCD or coil (13.5%), tubal ligation (12%), Diaphragm (12.2%), and male sterilization (10.6%).

A comparison of the responses of both male and female and across the two areas did not show any disparity (Undelikwo et al., 2013).

Studies done in Calabar showed that majority of the women are quite knowledgeable about contraceptives. About 92.1% are aware of contraceptives with health workers as their major source of information (34.3%) (Eko *et al.*, 2013). In that research, a cross sectional survey of 305 respondents who were selected using a multi-stage stratified sampling technique was done in Calabar metropolis concerning the prevalence of contraceptive use among women of reproductive age (15-49yrs.).

This study, however, did not assess the knowledge on each of the individual methods of contraceptive as knowledge of one method does not imply good knowledge on other methods. In order to improve the current level of awareness and utilization of contraceptives methods, it will be necessary to deliver accurate and timely information about reproductive health, safe motherhood and family planning using the channels that are most accessible to them which was found to be through radio programs and health workers (Solomon et al., 2010).

2.4 Prevalence of use of Family Planning Services

Globally, there is an increase in the utilization of family planning services. A 1993 united nations (UN) assessment of contraceptive prevalence estimates for the world by region giving low, medium, and high assumptions, confirms a global trend towards rising contraceptive use and declining fertility (Eko *et al.*, 2013). A World Health Organization (WHO) report in 2015 showed that the use of modern family planning method has risen from 54% in 1990 to 57.4% in 2014 globally (World Health Organisation, 2015).

About 64% of married or in-union women of reproductive age worldwide were using some form of family planning method, and of this, 57% use a modern method (Population Reference Bureau, 2013). Among major regions in the world where family planning use was much higher, rates ranging from 59% in Oceanic to 75% in North America were observed. It however remained relatively low in least developed countries especially in Africa with a rate of 33% (United Nations, 2015). Countries like Senegal still show a low uptake in adoption of modern family planning method use while Kenya showed rate leveled off in recent years but its peak was relatively low

compared to other countries of the world (Eko *et al.*, 2013). Studies by National Demographic and Health Survey also showed increase in the use of family planning methods from 13% in 2003 to 15% among married women in 2013 (NDHS, 2013). A study on factors influencing the uptake of modern family planning methods among women of reproductive age in a rural community in Lagos state recorded a contraceptive prevalence rate of 38.6% (Oluwole *et al.*, 2013).

Whereas in Cross River State, Calabar metropolis to be precise point prevalence of 21.6% was noted (Eko *et al.*, 2013). Although there seems to be a relative increase in family planning method utilization, especially in the south western part of the country, the overall picture is still lower than sub-Saharan average of 17.7%. this is notwithstanding the high level of awareness and knowledge of family planning services in the country. This has an inverse relationship with the birth rate on the country with total fertility rate as high as 5.5% in the country (NDHS, 2013).

2.5 Preferred Family Planning Methods

There are numerous methods of family planning available today. This can be divided broadly into two groups; modern and traditional methods. The modern methods include female sterilization, male sterilization, intrauterine contraceptive device (IUCD), implants, injectables, pills, male condoms, female condoms, emergency contraception, and lactational amenorrhoea method (LAM), whereas traditional methods include rhythmic (calendar), withdrawal, and folk methods (Central Statistical Agency and Demographic Health Survey, Ethiopia, 2016). However, for the sake of assessing preferred family methods used, family planning methods may be divided into modern methods, total long lasting reversible contraceptives, total permanent methods, male and female forms of sterilization, intrauterine devices, injectables, pills, male and female condoms, and other modern methods. Studies have shown that the more developed nations preferred the use of modern family planning methods (Population Reference Bureau, 2013; NDHS, 2013). Family planning data sheet report of 2013 showed that married women in developed countries using family planning services, most preferred method was modern contraceptive method with a rate of 57% followed by total permanent method (21%). Least used methods were other modern methods (2%). Less developed countries also showed similar trend with the developed countries (Population Reference Bureau, 2013). In Nigeria, most preferred method was modern methods

(10%), least preferred method was male sterilization (approx.0.01%) (Population Reference Bureau, 2013).

More succinctly, National Demographic and Health Survey in 2013, reported that modern methods were preferred (10%), followed by traditional methods (5%), followed by male condoms and pills (each 2%) (NDHS,2013).

A study conducted at Ibadan on the knowledge and utilization of family planning among married women comprising 136 participants showed that 22.8% used injectables contraceptives, 16% used IUCD, while implants, tubal ligation and *coitus interruptus* were the least used by women in the area (Lasisi, 2014). This is in line with the FPS and NDHS in 2013.

In Cross River State, studies have shown that the trend is similar to the aforementioned studies conducted in other parts of the country. For instance, a retrospective study in Cross River State on utilization and discontinuation of contraceptive methods showed IUCD (32.8%), injectables (23.8%), pills (21.5%), implants (20.5%), bi-tubal ligation (1.3%), condoms (2%) (Njoku et al., 2014).

Meaning that the respondents largely discontinued the use of IUCD at a rate (32.8%) and very less likely to discontinue the utilization of condoms at discontinuation rate of 2%. This is corroborated by another study on the prevalence of contraceptive use among women of reproductive age in Calabar metropolis as male condoms received higher prevalence of 29.3% followed by pills which was 21.3% (Eko *et al.*, 2013). From the above studies, preferred method of contraception is the modern contraceptive method. This is irrespective of what form of modern method utilized most. The choice of factors such as socio-economic status, ease of use, effectiveness, perceived side effects duration or action, interference with sexual intercourse, religions and cultural beliefs, future needs for fertility and so on.

2.6 Factors that Influence the Utilization of Family Planning Services

The attitude, knowledge and practice of family planning is a worldwide phenomenon as it cuts across all races, ages and religions etc. The prevalence of family planning is noted to be low from the studies above in sub Saharan Africa (Nigeria inclusive). This is despite the high level of knowledge and awareness of it. This knowledge-utilization gap has been shown to be as a result of

several factors militating against the use of family planning services. Several studies have shown these factors to include socio-demographic factors encompassing age, marital status, educational level, religion, and occupation, client related factors including awareness and knowledge of family planning, fear of side effects, partner consent, desire for more children, facility-related factors, accessibility of family planning facility, cost of family planning services.

A study on adolescents and utilization of family planning services in rural community of Nigeria reported education and income as important determinants of use of family planning (Isonguyio *et al.*, 2013). This is corroborated by another study which showed contraceptive use increase with education. 37% of married women with more than secondary education used any method, compared with 3% of married with no education (NDHS, 2013). Family planning use is high among women from wealthy household (NDHS,2013).

Although, it is important to look beyond individual factors when examining family planning use and non-use (Tsui *et al.*, 2010). Another impediment to family planning is fear of side effects. A study conducted in Uganda listed fear of side effects as the main impediment to family planning (Orach *et al.*, 2015). It has been noted that African men play important roles in the decision about family life including fertility and family planning. Also the desire for a child of a particular sex, example, the desire for male children may greatly affect use of contraceptive (Khanum *et al.*,2010). The consequence of high sexual activity and low contraceptive use leads to an increase frequency of unplanned pregnancy and subsequent induced abortions. The reason for this low contraceptive use were fear of side effects, objection from partners, conflict with religious belief, objection from family members not thinking about using contraceptives, not having intercourse to have a baby and unplanned debut (Monjok *et al.*, 2010).

Generally, use of any method and use of modern methods increased with education. Use of contraceptive was also positively related to wealth status, increase from 14% among married women in the lowest wealth quantile to 31% in the highest wealth quartile (Osakinle *et al.*, 2013). Religious beliefs and religion are suggested as key predictors of contraceptives utilization (Monjok *et al.*, 2010; Osuafor and Mturi, 2013). Also, limited availability, quality, and cost of family planning services are noted as influential factors (Monjok *et al.*, 2010).

From the above collections of studies, it is clear that though there lies a glaring disparity in the level at which certain factors influenced choice of a particular contraceptive method, there is a common denominator cutting across races, ages, cultures and religions. And that is, that there is always a limitation to use or disuse of every form of contraceptive method. This is so because none is ideal.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Settings

The study area was Nyaghasang community, in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. It is one of the communities in Calabar, Cross River State. They speak Efik and Ejagham. The community is bounded in the North by Ikot Omin, in the South by Calabar south, in the East by Ikot Offiong and in the west by Edibe Qua Town, with a total population of approximately 12,000 people. Politically it comprises ward 3 Calabar Municipality Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Nyaghasang is densely populated by the Efik and Ejagam nations. There are also non-indigenous inhabitants of the community (Ibibio, Igbo, Hausa, and Yoruba). There are road networks linking the community within. Most houses in the area are concrete buildings while a few have local mud outlay. Water supply is through borehole. Toilet used is water closet and ventilation improved pit latrine.

The people are mainly civil servants, traders. Amenities available in the community include Primary Health Care Center and also public and private schools, markets, churches.

3.2 Study Design

A descriptive cross sectional study was done for the determination of both family planning prevalence and factors affecting utilization of family planning services.

3.3 Study Population

Women in Nyaghasang community within the reproductive age group of 15-49 years.

3.4 Target Population

The target population include women of Nyaghasang community

3.5 Eligibility Criteria

3.5.1 Inclusion Criteria

All women within the reproductive age who gave consent were eligible to participate.

3.5.2 Exclusion Criteria

The following categories of women were excluded from this study;

1. Women within reproductive age who do not give consent
2. Women with known history of primary or secondary infertility.
3. Women who have undergone gynecological operation leading to permanent sterility but not done for contraceptive purpose.

3.6 Sample Size Determination

Cochran formula was used to determine the minimum sample size for qualitative data. This formula was used because the target population was more than 10,000. The formula is written as follows

$$n = Z^2Pq/d^2$$

Where, n= minimal sample size

Z=standard normal deviate=1.96

P= prevalence of use of any family planning method in women age 15 to 49 years is 12% (NDHS, 2018)

Q = proportion of failure (1-P) = (1-0.12) = 0.88

d = precision of study ±0.05

$$n = (1.96)^2 \times (0.12) \times (0.88) / (0.05)^2$$

$$n=164$$

$$10\% \text{ of } 164 = 16.4$$

Total number of sample = $164 + 16.4 = 180.4$

Hence, minimum sample size was 180.4

3.7 Sampling Method

A simple random sampling method was used. This was done by "spin the bottle method", where a bottle was spun at the center of the town hall and the streets where the head and tail of the bottle faced were used and households on those streets served as sampling frame, devoid of bias and serving equal probability for each household to be selected.

3.8 Data Collection Tool

Semi-structured questionnaire was used to elicit information from respondents. Questionnaire was written in English language and designed to collect information concerning the socio-demographic information of the respondents, knowledge and attitude of respondents towards family planning, practice of family planning, availability of family planning services and the factors influencing the utilization of family planning services in Nyaghasang Community.

Questionnaire was pretested in Edim Otop Community, Calabar Municipal Local Government Area. This exercise helped to improve the data collection tools in terms of content, reliability, validity and order of the questions in relation to the study objectives and necessary adjustments were made prior to final distribution to respondents in the study area. Questionnaires were distributed by members of group 2 of 2019/20 class.

3.9 Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the University of Calabar Teaching Hospital. Ethical Committee and clearance was also obtained from State Ethical Board and State Ministry of Health. The traditional chiefs and the youth leader of Nyaghasang were duly informed and consent was obtained from them. Informed verbal consent was obtained from all participants before administration of the questionnaire. They were informed about the purpose of the study and their right to abandon the process at any point. In a bid to ensure anonymity and confidentiality, information on names and other identification forms were not included in the questionnaire and they were kept safely after being filled.

3.10 Data Analysis and Presentation

Data analysis was done by using IBM-Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) software version 25. Frequencies of variables, measures of central tendencies and dispersions including means and standard deviation were generated; tabulations and percentages were used to illustrate study findings and P-value<0.05 was considered statistically significantly associated with the outcome variable.

Inferential statistical techniques, chi square test and likelihood ratio test were adopted to test the relationships.

3.11 Duration of Study

This study lasted for a period of at least four months (September , 2019-May, 2021).

RESULTS

This chapter presents results and analysis of findings. A total of 180 women of reproductive age (15-49years) were surveyed.

4.1 Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

The socio-demographic characteristics of respondents in Nyaghasang, Calabar, who volunteered in this study is as presented in Table 1 below. A total of one hundred and eighty (180) women of reproductive age were interviewed. The mean age of the respondents was 28.98 ± 8.177 years, with majority of the respondents 120(66.7%) within the 14-31 range. A higher proportion of those interviewed were single 86(47.8%) followed closely by married women 72(40%). Majority of them had secondary and tertiary levels of education 89, 76(49.4%, 42.2%) respectively while 1(0.6%) had no formal education. 90(50%) were self-employed while 23 (12.8%) were civil servants, predominantly Christians 154(85.6%). As many as 156(86.7%) earn average of below 45000 per month. 84 (46.7%) had no children.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY (n=180)	PERCENTAGE (%)
Age group		
14-31	120	66.7
32-49	60	33.3
Mean age \pm Standard deviation	28.98 \pm 8.177	
Marital status		
Single	86	47.8
Marital	72	40
Cohabiting	16	8.9
Divorce/Separated/Widow	6	3.3
Educational level		
None	1	0.6
Primary	14	7.8
Secondary	89	49.4
Tertiary	76	42.2
Occupation		
Civil servant	23	12.8
Public worker	14	7.8
Self employed	90	50.0
House wife	23	12.8
Unemployed	12	6.6
Others	18	10.0
Religion		
Christianity	154	85.6
Islam	26	14.4
Average income (Naira)		
0-45,000	156	86.7
46,000-90,000	20	11.1
Number of children		
None	84	46.7
1-3	71	39.4
4-6	25	13.9

4.2 Awareness of Family Planning

Awareness of Family Planning among respondents as shown (Fig. 1) revealed that majority 158(88%) were already aware of Family Planning, while 22(12%) responded having no knowledge of family planning.

Figure I: Showing Awareness of Family Planning Amongst Respondents

4.3 Source of Information of Family Planning

Majority 108(60%) of respondents in this study volunteered that they got their knowledge of family planning from their peers and relatives, 98(54%) of them identified health personnel, 50(27.8%) each mentioned church and electronic, as their information sources as shown in Fig. II

Figure ii: Showing Sources of Information of Family Planning amongst Respondents

4.4 Knowledge and Attitude Towards Family Planning

Table 2 revealed that more than two-third majority 139(77.2%) believed that family planning is good while a third 41(22.8%) of them believed the contrary.

Table 2: Knowledge and Attitude Towards Family Planning

VARIABLE	YES	NO	TOTAL
	FREQUENCY (%)	FREQUENCY (%)	FREQUENCY (%)
Awareness of Side Effects of Family Planning	158 (88)	34(12)	180(100)
Perception of Family Planning	146(81.1)	34(18.9)	180(100)
Knowledge of Side Effects of Family Planning;			
Menstrual disturbances	116(64.4)	64(35.6)	180(100)
Weight gain	59(32.8)	121(67.2)	180(100)
Headache	26(14.4)	154(85.6)	180(100)
Dizziness	36(20.0)	142(80.0)	180(100)
Breast tenderness	38(21.1)	142(78.9)	180(100)
Mood swings	22(12.3)	157(87.7)	180(100)
Decreased libido	20(11.6)	159(88.4)	180(100)
Vaginal discharge	45(25.0)	135(75.0)	180(100)

PREVALENCE OF FAMILY PLANNING IN NYAGHASANG COMMUNITY

Figure III revealed that majority 106(59%) of the respondents were not on any form of contraception while only 74 (41%) of the participants were using one form of family planning or the other.

Figure iii: Showing Prevalence of Family Planning in Nyaghasang Community

PRACTICE OF FAMILY PLANNING

Table 3. showed that most 111(61.7%) of the family planning materials were sourced from Health Centers and Hospitals. Condoms 34(18.9%) being the most used form of family planning, followed by Calendar method 26(14.4%) while diaphragms 1(0.6%), IUCDs 3(1.7%) and surgical or permanent methods 4(2.2%) are the least patronized.

Menstrual disturbances 15(8.3%) and breast tenderness 8(4.4%) were perceived to be the major side effects experienced by a fraction of the respondents. And 16(8.9%) of the sample population had changed from one form of family planning to another due to side effects from previous form.

Table 3: Practice of Family Planning, Sources, Methods and Side Effects

VARIABLE	YES	NO	TOTAL
	FREQUENCY (%)	FREQUENCY (%)	FREQUENCY (%)
Source;			
Health Centre/Hospital	111(61.7)	69(38.3)	180(100)
Chemist/Pharmacy	41(22.8)	139(77.2)	180(100)
Family/Friends/Relatives	26(14.4)	154(85.6)	180(100)
Others	2(1.1)	178(98.9)	180(100)
Method;			
Condoms	34(18.9)	146(81.1)	180(100)
Diaphragm	1(0.6)	179(99.4)	180(100)
Injectable	5(2.8)	175(97.2)	180(100)
Pills	15(8.3)	165(91.7)	180(100)
Implants	13(7.2)	167(92.8)	180(100)
Surgery	4(2.2)	176(97.8)	180(100)
IUD	3(1.7)	177(98.3)	180(100)
Withdrawal	12(6.7)	168(93.3)	180(100)
LAM	2(1.1)	178(98.9)	180(100)
Calendar	26(14.4)	154(85.6)	180(100)
Others	2(1.1)	178(98.9)	180(100)
Family Planning Side Effects;			
Weight Gain	7(3.9)	173(96.1)	180(100)
Menstrual Disturbances	15(8.3)	165(91.7)	180(100)
Headache	1(0.6)	179(99.4)	180(100)
Dizziness	2(1.1)	178(98.9)	180(100)
Breast Tenderness	8(4.4)	172(95.6)	180(100)
Mood Swings	3(1.7)	177(98.3)	180(100)
Decreased Libido	1(0.6)	179(99.4)	180(100)
Others	6(33.3)	174(96.7)	180(100)
Change of Family Planning method	16(8.9)	164(91.1)	180(100)

PREFERRED FORM OF FAMILY PLANNING METHOD USED IN NYAGHASANG COMMUNITY

Fig. IV revealed that 37% of the respondents preferred condoms to other form of family planning with surgical methods and diaphragms suffering the worse patronage

Figure iv: Showing the Preferred Form of Family Planning Method used by Respondents

BARRIERS TO UTILIZATION OF FAMILY PLANNING

Table 4. showed the respondents views on possible barriers to their utilization of family planning. These revealed the following; all the factors listed were not seen by majority as a possible barrier to their utilization of family planning. On the whole, only 76(42.2%) of the respondents nodded to “*fear of side effects*” as being a barrier to their utilization of family planning. It also revealed that accessibility to health 16(8.9%), religion 25(13.9%), cultural norms 10(5.6%) and financial cost 35(19.4%) are far less likely seen as barriers to their effective utilization of family planning.

BARRIERS TO UTILIZATION OF FAMILY PLANNING

Table 4. Barriers to use of Family Planning Methods

VARIABLE	YES(%)	NO(%)	Total(%)
Religion	25(13.9)	155(86.1)	180(100)
Cultural Norms	10(5.6)	170(94.4)	180(100)
Partner's Consent	40(22.2)	140(77.8)	180(100)
Fear Of Side Effect(s)	76(42.2)	104(57.8)	180(100)
Financial Cost	35(19.4)	145(80.6)	180(100)
Accessibility To Health	16(8.9)	164(91.1)	180(100)
Others	9(5.0)	171(95.0)	180(100)

KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE OF WOMEN TOWARDS FAMILY PLANNING

Fig. V shows the level of knowledge and attitude that our respondents had about family planning. The respondents were tested using an eleven (11) item questionnaire on their level of knowledge and attitude towards family planning. One point is scored for each correct answer and scores were based on their responses to the test tool; a score ≤ 5 is recorded as poor knowledge, 6-9 as fair knowledge and a score ≥ 10 was regarded as good knowledge of family planning. The simple test tool, therefore, showed that only one-sixth 32(18%) of the study sample had good knowledge, 49(27%) had fair knowledge while majority 99(55%) had poor knowledge of family planning.

Figure V: Knowledge and Attitude of Women towards Family Planning

ASSOCIATION OF SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHICS AND KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE OF WOMEN TOWARDS FAMILY PLANNING SERVICES

Table 5. showed a statistically significant association between respondents' educational level and religion with their level of knowledge and attitude towards family planning services. However, their knowledge and attitudes towards family planning services did not portray this statistical significance with the demographics of age, marital status, number of children, occupation and their average monthly earnings.

Table 5: Association of Socio-demographics and knowledge & attitude of women towards family planning services

VARIABLE	POOR KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE (%)	FAIR KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE (%)	GOOD KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE (%)	CHI-SQUARE	P-VALUE
Age group					
14-31	72(62.6%)	40(71.4%)	5.0(83.3%)	2.130	0.345
32-49	43(37.4%)	16(28.6%)	1.0(16.7%)		
Marital status					
Single	57(49.6%)	26(46.4%)	2.2(33.3%)	8.917	0.178
Married	46(40.0%)	23(41.1%)	2.0(33.3%)		
Cohabiting	10(8.7%)	3(5.4%)	2.0(33.3%)		
Divorce/Separated/	2.0(1.7%)	4(7.1%)	0.0(0.00%)		
Widow					
Educational level					
None	1.0(0.9%)	0(0.0%)	0.0(0.00%)	11.927	0.064
Primary	9.0(7.8%)	4.(7.1%)	0.0 (0.00%)		
Secondary	66(57.4%)	21(37.5%)	1.0(16.7%)		
Tertiary	39(33.9%)	31(55.4%)	5.0(83.3%)		
Occupation					
Civil servant	11(9.6%)	11(19.6%)	0.0(0.00%)	8.959	0.536
Public worker	7.0(6.1%)	6(10.7%)	1.0(16.7%)		
Self employed	59(51.3%)	25(44.6%)	4(66.7%)		
House wife	15(13.0%)	7(12.5%)	1.0(16.7%)		
Unemployed	10(8.7%)	2(3.6%)	0.0(0.0%)		
Others	13(11.3%)	5(8.9%)	0.0(0.0%)		
Religion					
Christianity	26(22.6%)	30(53.6%)	4(66.7%)	19.816	0.001*
Islam	88(76.5%)	25(44.6%)	2(33.3%)		
Others	1.0(0.9%)	1(1.8%)	0.0(0.00%)		
Average income (₦)					
0-45,000	104(92%)	43(79.6%)	6(100%)	6.313	0.043*
46,000-90,000	9.0(8.0%)	11(20.4%)	0.0(0.0%)		
Number of children					
None	52(45.2%)	28(50.0%)	4(66.7%)	4.763	0.312
1-3	43(37.4%)	24(42.9%)	2(33.3%)		
4-6	20(17.4%)	4.0(7.1%)	0.0(0.0%)		

Association of socio-demographics and Prevalence of Family Planning

Table 6 showed a significant association between socio-demographics and prevalence of family planning among respondents. Revealing that marital status (*P-value* 0.030) is a statistically significant socio-demographic variable when related with prevalence of family planning. Whereas respondents age, educational level, occupation, average income, religion and number of children were not statistically significant.

Table 6: Association of Socio demographics and Prevalence of Family Planning.

VARIABLE	NON-USE (%)	USE (%)	CHI-SQUARE	P-VALUE
Age group				
14-31	77(64.2%)	43(35.8%)	3.330	0.068
32-49	30(50.0%)	30(50.0%)		
Marital status				
Single	59(68.6%)	27(31.4%)	8.972	0.030*
Married	39(54.2%)	33(45.8%)		
Cohabiting	8.0(50.0%)	8.0(50.0%)		
Divorce/Separated/Widow	1.0(16.7%)	5.0(83.3%)		
Educational level				
None	1.0(100%)	0.0(0%)	1.133	0.679
Primary	9(64.3%)	5(35.7%)		
Secondary	54(60.7%)	35(39.3%)		
Tertiary	43(56.6%)	33(43.4%)		
Occupation				
Civil servant	8.0(34.8%)	15(65.2%)	10.750	0.057
Public worker	7.0(50.0%)	7.0(50.0%)		
Self employed	56(62.2%)	34(37.8%)		
House wife	13(56.5%)	10(43.5%)		
Unemployed	10(83.3%)	2.0(16.7%)		
Others	13(72.2%)	5.0(27.8%)		
Religion				
Christianity	35(56.5%)	27(43.5%)	0.454	0.979
Islam	71(61.2%)	45(38.2%)		
Others	1.0(50.0%)	1.0(50.0%)		
Average income (Naira)				
0-45,000	97(62.2%)	59(37.8%)	3.623	0.057
46,000-90,000	8.0(40.0%)	12(60.0%)		
Number of children				
None	56(66.7%)	28(33.3%)	3.425	0.180
1-3	38(53.5%)	33(45.6%)		
4-6	13(52.0%)	12(48.0%)		

Table 7: ASSOCIATION OF BARRIERS TO UTILIZATION AND PREVALENCE OF FAMILY PLANNING

VARIABLE+	NON –USE (%)	USE (%)	CHI-SQUARE	P-VALUE
Barrier				
Religion	11(44%)	14(56)%	3.149	0.076
Cultural Norms	4(40%)	6(60%)	1.661	0.198
Partner’s Consent	22(55.0%)	18(45.0%)	0.375	0.538
Fear Of Side Effect(s)	38(51.3%)	37(48.7%)	3.415	0.065
Financial Cost	16(45.7%)	19(54.3%)	3.173	0.075
Accessibility To Health	7(43.8%)	9(56.3%)	1.794	0.180

DISCUSSION

5.1 Knowledge and attitude towards family planning

A high level of knowledge of family planning was recorded in this study with 158(88%) of participants knowing about family planning. This is in corroboration with studies conducted within and outside Nigeria including the most recent NDHS (2013) survey which puts the level awareness of at least one family planning method among Nigerians females at 85%. This pattern is expected with the ongoing sensitization and increased dissemination of information on benefits of family planning globally, especially in affected regions (Oluwole *et al*, 2013).

Contrary to studies that points to mass media as the primary source of information about family planning (NDHS, 2013), the predominant source of information dissemination about family planning in this study was from respondents' relatives and friends 110(61.1%) whereas 98(54.4%) mentioned health facility as their source of information. This may be in one part, through family meetings, committee of friends meetings and health-related campaigns or during visits to health facilities and secondly might be largely due the fact majority 86(47.8%) of the participants were single women within the age bracket of (15-31years). This is in keeping with studies conducted among women in Lagos (Oluwole *et al*, 2016) and Calabar (Eko *et al*, 2013). This pattern of result is a pointer to the importance of enhanced primary health care services in the different communities. Although health facilities ranked second in our study, it is important to promote and sustain policies and efforts geared towards increasing knowledge and attitude of family planning in our health facilities. Our study also showed a significant role of churches 50(27.8%) in enhancing knowledge and attitude of family planning in the society. Similarly, our study revealed a statistically significant relationship between religion (66.7%, $P=0.001^*$), monthly income of respondents and their level of knowledge and attitude towards family planning services. It showed that 92% people whose monthly income was below N45,000 (92%) were more likely to have poor knowledge of family planning than those who earned more than N45,000 monthly. Showing that religion is significant as 66.7% of our respondents were more likely to have good knowledge and attitude towards family planning services than none Christians. This might be linked to the role of the church as a source of information about family planning services.

Modern methods of family planning were shown to be the more popular methods of family planning among participants in this study. Condoms recorded the highest with an awareness rate of 34(18.9%) followed by Calendar 26(14%) and pills 15(8.3%). This is different from a survey carried out by NDHS (2013), among women of reproductive age which showed that although modern family planning were the most acknowledged method, pills (71) were more common than injectables (68%) and male condoms (67%) (NDHS, 2013). The high level of popularity male condoms as a method of family planning in this study may be because it is cheap, more easily accessible, more advertised and affords some level of protection against sexually transmitted diseases especially HIV/AIDS. Very few of study participants acknowledge natural and traditional method of family planning. This is in keeping with the global trend where the less efficacious traditional and natural methods of family planning are trailing way behind the more efficacious and convenient modern methods of family planning as seen in a Calabar based study by Eko et al., 2013 which revealed that Condom (50%), pills (36.6%), rhythmic method (33.4%), injectables (23.4%), withdrawal method (20.6%), and sterilization (10.6%).

During the course of this study, attitude of participants towards family planning was assessed. A vast majority of study participants 139(77.2%) that were aware of family planning described it as being good. They cited birth spacing, control of unwanted pregnancies and prevention of sexually transmitted infections as their reasons. This is in accordance with other similar studies conducted by Oluwole et al 2016; Isonguyio et al 2013; and Eko et al 2013.

Twenty-two percent of participants that were aware of family planning said that it was bad. Side effect of family planning methods were the main reason. This is in keeping with study done at Lagos which showed that 38% said that family planning was bad because of the side effects (Oluwole *et al.*, 2013). This emphasizes the need for provision of adequate and accurate information about family planning with emphasis on the fact that there are different family planning methods each with its side effect profile that may be tolerated by different people based on their physiological and social status in the community.

This study showed that majority of participants 146(81.1%) that knew about family planning also had knowledge of the side effects of family planning methods. This is slightly higher than a study conducted in Pakistan which recorded a level of awareness of side effects of 41% (Haider *et al.*,

2009). This however may be attributed the fact that over 40% of the participants in this study had tertiary educational qualification as compared with the study in Pakistan where only 6% had tertiary education.

5.2 Prevalence Rate of Family Planning Utilization

The prevalence rate of family planning utilization in this study was 59%, that is, 106 study participants were on at least one form of family planning method at the time of this study. There is, therefore, an *awareness-practice mismatch* in this study 158-73(88%-40.6%). This is in keeping with a NDHS (2013) study which showed a higher level of family planning awareness but low level of utilization (NDHS, 2013). Similar findings were reported in another study conducted in Calabar in the year 2013 where a prevalence rate of 21.6% was observed with an awareness level of 92.1% (Eko *et al*, 2013). This high knowledge-utilization gap may be explained by factors that militate against the use of family planning especially their high level of awareness of the side effects may have discouraged them from utilizing family planning services.

Our study also revealed that marital status was statistically significant when related with prevalence of family planning ($P=0.003^*$). This implies that married respondents were more likely to utilize family planning services than those who were not married.

When the prevalence rate of family planning use of this study was compared to similar studies in other parts of the countries, it was seen to be relatively high. A study at Jigawa state showed a prevalence rate of 0.3% (Contraceptive Prevalence Rate, 2013). Another one conducted at Ibadan had a prevalence rate of 9% (Lasisi *et al*, 2014). This is in corroboration with an NDHS's (2013) study which showed that family planning prevalence rate varied in different regions of the countries, lowest in the north, highest in the south/western region of the county. More so, the participants in this study were probably more enlightened than those in the other studies, as greater than 40% of them had a tertiary level of educational qualification.

5.3 Most Preferred Forms of Family Planning Method

Most preferred forms of family planning methods in this study were modern methods with over one-quarter 75(64.1%) of the respondents who were on family planning method during the period of this study using one form of modern family planning method or the other. This is a reflection of the global pattern of contraceptive use which shows that 9 out of 10 women in their reproductive age, who are on family planning, are using modern methods of family planning (United Nations, 2015). Similar result was obtained in a study conducted at Lagos were modern family planning

prevalence rate was 85% among study population that used family planning (Oluwole *et al*, 2013). This pattern of use of family planning methods is expected in light of increased global campaigns on family planning, education and increased level of awareness of individuals about modern family planning methods (Oluwole *et al*, 2013).

More so, modern family planning methods are shown to have better efficacy, convenience and ease of use over the older traditional and natural methods thus, will be preferably used.

This study further showed that among participants that were using modern method, majority were using condoms (18.9%) followed by Calendar (14.4%) and pills (8.3%). This finding is corroborated by several studies (Oluwole *et al*, 2013; Egessa, 2016). This may be explained by the current HIV/AIDS pandemic and the role of condoms in minimizing its transmission. Furthermore, condoms are more affordable and accessible. In contrast to this finding, similar studies including an NDHS's (2013) survey showed that other forms of family planning methods including IUCDs, pills and injectables were utilized ahead of condoms (NDHS, 2013; PRB, 2013; Njoku *et al*, 2013). This may be due to the fact that these methods of contraception are more convenient to use with depot injectables given once in two months; IUCDs inserted once in five years and more so, do not seem to interfere with sexual satisfaction.

Least utilized modern family planning method was lactational amenorrhea method and IUCDs. However, the low level of use of intrauterine contraceptive device (1.7%) observed in this study is in sharp contrast with results of other studies including the one conducted in Calabar were IUCDs were the most prevalent method of family planning (Njoku *et al*, 2014). Its low level of use may be due to lack of information about them in this study area.

There was no recorded use of female surgical methods. Although this is shown be used quite frequently in more developed parts of the world. This is explained by the fact that most respondents utilize family planning for the sake of spacing child birth rather than limit family size and so would opt for methods that are easily reversible when necessary (Njoku *et al*, 2014).

5.4 Factors Influencing Utilization of Family Planning Services

Utilization rate of family planning services was shown to be relatively low 73(40.6%) especially when compared to the level of knowledge and awareness of family planning among study

population 158(88%). During the course of this study, factors affecting the utilization and uptake of family planning were identified and assessed including education, age, religion and so on.

5.4.1 Education

In this study, there was no statistically significant relationship between the level of education and utilization of family planning ($p=0.679$). Participants with at least a secondary educational qualification were expected to more likely to use family planning services when compared to those with a primary level of education or uneducated. Though this is not seen in our sample population. Hence, there is an awareness-utilization mismatch in the population we studied. Similar to a study conducted by Eko *et al*, 2013 which revealed the same pattern somewhere in Calabar.

5.4.3 Awareness of Family Planning

A statistically significant relationship was found between the awareness of family planning and current family planning use ($p = 0.003$). The study showed that participants that were aware of family planning were more likely to use family planning methods (88%) when compared to those who were not aware of it (12%). This is corroborated by similar study conducted in Calabar (Eko *et al*, 2013). This may be because participants that are not aware of family planning are far less likely to use family.

5.4.4 Attitude towards Family Planning

This study showed a significant relationship between attitude towards family planning and use of family planning ($p=0.005$). It showed that participants that agreed that family planning was good (92.8%) were more likely to use family planning than those that said it was bad (6.3%). This may be explained by the fact that a favourable attitude towards family planning increases the chances of use of family planning.

5.5 Barriers to use of Family Planning Services

This study went further to assess the reasons for non-use of family planning services by participants who were not on family planning during the study. The most common reason given

was fear of side effect (42.2%). Similar results have been obtained in similar studies (Njoku, 2015; Moronkola et al, 2006; Orach et al, 2015). This one of the most important reason for non-use of family planning in developing countries where there is a high knowledge-utilization dissociation (Eko et al, 2013). Proper information, education and a reorientation is required to dispel the myth of side effects of modern contraceptive especially that of infertility.

Partner's consent was also reported as a reason for non-use of family planning services by participants (15.7%) in this study. This is corroborated by several studies including one done at Ethiopia in 2006 where spousal consent vital in use of family planning services. It therefore becomes imperative to educate men on importance of family planning. This also stresses the importance of improving the educational and economic opportunities; bargaining power and independence of women during fertility reduction and family planning programs (Bandura, 2002).

Religion was also listed as a reason for non-use of family planning services by 13.2% of participant who were not on family planning during the period of this study. This is in keeping with results from similar studies where religion was one of the reasons for non-use of family planning (Oluwole et al, 2013; Nwachukwu et al). Muslims and Catholics have been known to oppose modern contraceptive methods as it is against their faith. In this study, more than 30% of participants were Catholics

Other reasons listed for non-adoption of family planning include desire for more children (9.3%), cost of family planning services (8.4%) and access to family planning services (7.6%). These are in keeping with results from similar studies including, Beekle (2006), Eko (2013) and Oluwole (2013).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The recommendations are proposed to Government, Family planning service providers, health facilities and other direct program implementers for improving use of Family Planning services in our society. In spite of the high level of awareness and knowledge of family planning, its utilization is still low. Other forms of family planning are still underutilized. There is, therefore, need to not only conduct family planning programs, but also invite family planning experts to provide method specific information on a wide range of family planning methods to help people know and choose a contraceptive method that may be more appropriate to individual health and living conditions and also address related safety concerns.
2. False belief, wrong information and misconception that are associated with the wrong perception and exaggeration of side effects of family planning should be addressed and dispelled. The potential side effects of contraceptives and how to overcome them should be incorporated into family planning education and Counselling.
3. Non-use of family planning as a result of religious belief can be addressed by providing accurate, method specific information on natural family planning methods including the billings, beads and the rhythm method. For non-use due to spousal consent it is important to implement different intervention programs that involve men and encourage couples to discuss about family planning. This has been shown to significantly increase family planning uptake.
4. Service delivery related factors such as access to wide range of Family Planning methods, family planning counseling were associated with family planning use. Re-education of, not only family planning personnel, but chemist and pharmacist is important as the main source of family planning was noted to be from private sources.
5. The current lack of political will in the aspects of family planning should be duly addressed. Government policies such as the incorporation of family planning education in secondary and tertiary curricula should be formulated. The government through the ministry of health and education should launch and fund appropriate researches to assess utilization rate, barriers to utilization of family planning and possible areas of intervention.

Appropriate surveillance and indicators should be put in place to ensure that goals and objectives are met and maintained.

REFERENCES

- Augustine, VU; Mathias, GA (2011). Contraception Awareness And Practice Among Antenatal Attendees in Uyo, Nigeria. *Pan Africa Journal of Medicine* 2011; 10:53.
- Dorothy S. 2010. "The ABC of Family Planning. Partnership For Material, Newborn & Child Health, Canada.
- Ekabua John E., Essien James E., Monjok Emmanuel, Smesny Andrea; "Contraceptive Practices in Nigeria; Literature And Recommendation For Future Policy Decisions"; *OPEN ACCESS JOURNAL OF CONTRACEPTION*; vol 1
- Eko JE, Osinwa KO, Osuchukwu "Prevalence of Contraceptive Use Among Women of Reproductive Age in Calabar Metropolis, Southern Nigeria. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNALS OF HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCE INVENTION* 2013
- Ekong I and Johnson O. 2015 "Knowledge, Attitude And Practice of Family Planning Among Women in a Rural Community in Southern Nigeria; *BRITISH JOURNAL OF MEDICINE AND MEDICAL RESEARCH* vol 12.vol
- Etukidem. A.J, W. Ndifon, J. Etowa and E.F. Asuquo 2017 "Family Planning Practices of Rural Community Dwellers in Cross River state, Nigeria; *NIGERIAN JOURNAL OF CLINICAL PRACTICE* 2017
- Family and Reproductive Health Journal 2017 National Conference, Washington DC.
- Haider, G; Parrean, N; Ranis A. (2009). Family Planning Practices Among Multiparous Women in Pakistan; ISRA University Hospital Library.
- Ibrahim, G; Ayyuba, R; Idris, SA (2013). Knowledge, Attitude And Practice of Contraceptives Among Grand Multifarious Women Attending Antenatal Clinic in a Specialist Hospital, Kano, Nigeria. *Niger J. Basic Clin. Sci.* 2015; 12:90
- Igwegbe, AO; Joseph, OU; Monago, EN (2009). Prevalence and Detrainments of Unmet Need For Family Planning in Nnewi; South-east Nigeria. *International Journal of Medicine & Medical Sciences. Vol 1 (8). Pp. 325-329, August, 2009.*
- Isonguyo, IN and Adindu, A (2013). "Adolescent and Utilization of Family Planning Services in Rural Community of Nigeria. *Research on Humanities and Social Science* vol,3 no 1.

- Johnson O, and Ekong I. (2015), Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of Family Planning Among Women of Reproductive Age in a Rural Community in Southern Nigeria: A British Journal of Medicine & Medical Research; vol. 12, No.2, pp 1-8.
- Khanum, S; Krishanan, S; Chandra, PS and Padian, NS (2010). Clinical progress in Obsteric and Gynaecology. Epub 2010 vol. 25 (9): 1594-611.
- Lasis, CJ; Bassey, TI; Ita, AE; Awoyeni, OK (2014) “Awareness and Utilization of Family Planning Among Married Women In The Traditional Area of Ibandan, Oyo State”. NOVA Journal of Humanities and Sciences, vol.3/ No.2 pp 1-8
- Lwelamira, J; Mnyamagola, G; Msaki, MM (2012). Knowledge, Attitude and Practice (KAP) Towards Modern Contraceptives Among Married Women of Reproductive Age in Mpwapwa District, Central Tanzania. Current Research Journal of social Science 4 (3): 235-345,2012.
- Mosher, WD; Jones, J. (2010). Use of Contraceptive in The United State; 1982-2008. National Center For Health Statistic. Vital Health State. 23 (29).
- Muluwas A; Muluemebet A.; Misra A, (2015). Utilization of Family Planning Services And Influences Factors Among Women of Child Bearing Age in Assosa District, Benishangul Gumuz Regional State, West Ethopia. *Science Journal of Clinical Medicine*.
- Njoku, CO; Emechebe, CI; Ekabua JE and Abeshi, S. 2014 “Utilization and Discontinuation of contraceptive methods: The University of Calabar Teaching Hospital (UCTH) experience. Global Journal of medicine and public Health, vol. 3, No5
- National Population Commission (2011)
- Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (2013)
- Oluwole, EO; Kuyinu, YA; Godman, OO; Odugbe, MI; Akinyima, MR (2016). Factors influencing uptake of Modern Family Planning Method Among Women of Reproductive Age in a Rural Community in Lagos State. International Journal of Tropical Disuses and Health 11(3): 1-11.
- Okonofua, FE; Shittu, SO; Oronsaye, F; Ogunshakin, D; Ogonwan, S and Zayyan, M (2009) Attitude and Practice of Private Medical Providers Towards Family Planning and Abortion Services in Nigeria. *Acta Obstetric Gynescand*. 84:270-280.
- Orach, CG, Otim, G; Apromon, JF and Amone, R. (2015). Perception, Attitude and Use of Family Planning Service in Post Conflict Gulu District, Northern Uganda. Research Gate Journal of Conflict and Health. Vol 9(1): 24. Dec., 2015

Osakinle EO; Babatunde JO; Alade FA, (2013). Youths and Their Choice of Contraceptives Toward an Effective Reproductive Health. A Case Study of Ekiti State, Nigeria. *European Scientific Journal*, 9:9.

Osuafor, GN and Mturi, A (2013). "Do Religious Beliefs Influence Use of Contraceptive Among Currently Married Women in Nigeria". *Journal of Social Development in Africa*, 28 (1):187-121

Palermo T, Jennifer B, Elizabeth W. (2014). Knowledge And Use of Emergency Contraception. A Multi-country Analysis. *International Prospective on Sexual and Reproductive Health* 2014, 40 (2): 79-86 doi

APPENDIX

CONSENT FORM

We are final year students of the Department of Community Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, University of Calabar. This course requires us to conduct a research project on the topic Knowledge, Attitude and practice of Family Planning Among Women of Reproductive Age (15-49 years) in Nyaghasang Community, Calabar.

The objective of this study is to determine the level of awareness and practice of family planning services in among women of reproductive age in Nyaghasang Community, Calabar, Cross River State.

This questionnaire serves as a means of data collection to enable the completion of the project. It contains both open and closed ended questions to enable you elaborate your response.

CONFIDENTIALITY

Information obtained will be treated with utmost confidentiality and shall be used strictly for research purposes. Names will not be required from you. Participation is voluntary. You are hereby informed that you do not have to answer a question you do not want to and you may also end this interview at any point you choose to. However, your honest cooperation is profoundly appreciated.

CONSENT

I have read the description of this research and understood it. I understand that my participation is voluntary and I retain the right to opt out of this exercise at any point without any consequences. I have received a copy of this consent form and by signing have offered to participate in the research project.

Signature of Respondent..... Date.....

Time issued.....

Student's Registration Number.....

QUESTIONNAIRE

**KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE OF FAMILY PLANNING AMONG
WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE IN NYAGHASANG COMMUNITY, CALABAR.**

Instructions: Please encircle the response as appropriate or specify where required.

SECTION A: SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

1. Age at last birthday
2. Marital status: i. Single ii. Married iii. Cohabiting iv. Divorced/Separated/Widow
3. What is your educational level: i. None ii. Primary iii. Secondary iv. Tertiary
4. Occupation: i. Civil servant ii. Public servant iii. Self-employed iv. House wife v. Unemployed
5. What is your religion: i. Christianity ii. Islam iii. Traditional iv. Others
6. Average monthly income.....
7. Number of Children..... i. None ii. 1-3 iii. 4-6

SECTION B KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS FAMILY PLANNING

8. Have you ever heard about family planning i. Yes ii. No
9. If YES, from where? (tick as many as appropriate) i. Electronic Media ii. Books iii. Health personnel iv. Friends/Relatives v. Social media vi. Church
10. Do you think family planning is good? i. Yes ii. No If yes give reason(s).....

If NO give reasons.....
.....

11. Are you aware of the side effects of family planning methods i. Yes ii. No
12. If yes, which one do you know about? (tick as many as appropriate) i. Menstrual disturbance ii. Weight gain iii. Headache iv. Dizziness v. Breast tenderness vi. Mood swings vii. Decreased libido viii. Vaginal discharge ix. Others (please specify).....

SECTION C: PRACTICE OF FAMILY PLANNING

13. Are you currently on any form of family planning method? i. Yes ii. No
14. IF YES, where did you get it from? i. Health centre/Hospital ii. Pharmacy/Chemist iii. Family/friends/relatives iv. Traditional practitioners vi. Others(please specify)
15. WHAT METHODS ARE YOU CURRENTLY ON? i. Condoms ii. Diaphragm iii. Injections iv. Pills v. Implants vi. Surgery vii. Intrauterine device viii. Withdrawal method ix. Lactational amenorrhea method (LAM) x. Calendar method xi. Other please specify.....
16. Do you have any side effects from the family planning method you are using? i. Yes ii. No
17. If yes, which of them (tick as many as appropriate) i. weight gain ii. Menstrual disturbances iii. Headache iv. Dizziness v. Breast tenderness vi. Mood swings vii. Decreased libido viii. Vaginal discharge x. Others (please specify).....
18. Have you ever changed from one family planning method to another? i. Yes ii. No
If yes, why.....
19. How do you find the use of family planning? i. Beneficial ii. Non beneficial
Give reasons for your answer.....
20. What is your belief on Family Planning?.....

SECTION D-BARRIERS TO UTILIZATION OF FAMILY PLANNING SERVICES

21. Which of the following factor(s) would discourage your use of contraceptives? (You can tick as many options as they affect you? i. Religion ii. Cultural norms iii. Partner’s consent iv. Previous side effect v. Fear of side effect vi. Desire for more children vii. Ease of use of family planning viii. Financial cost ix. Accessibility to health facility x. Others (please specify).....

Thank you for your time and response.

